

Beyond Pollution: Gender, Social Reproduction, and Legal Systems as Sites of Environmental Injustice

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Abstract:

This paper centers the experiences of Iranian women to rethink the place of gender in environmental justice studies. Although environmental justice movements have long been shaped by the activism of women, gender and sexuality have remained marginal concerns within the academic field. This paper argues that Iranian women's experience and struggles against discriminatory legal systems offer a crucial lens through which environmental justice can be reconceptualized. Drawing on narratives sourced from news outlets and social media, this paper shows how legal inequalities produce specific forms of environmental harm. Laws that degrade women's legal status contribute to environmental injustices by endangering lives, injuring bodies, interrupting daily subsistence, and enabling various forms of confinement. These harms must be recognized not only as social or legal issues but as environmental consequences. I propose that feminist environmental justice scholarship must confront the politics of scale and social reproduction, and expand its definition of "environment" and "environmental harm" to account for the embodied and spatial impacts of legal discrimination. The paper also suggests that the Iranian feminist movement offers valuable lessons for the environmental movement, which can be effectively transferred only by recognizing critical arenas for understanding environmental justice.

Keywords: Iran, environmental justice, women, gender and sexuality, bodily scale, social reproduction

Introduction

Environmental justice as a field of action owes much to women's activism. However, as an academic field, it still lacks sufficient attention to issues of gender and sexuality. In Iran, the concept of environmental justice (EJ) is relatively new. Originating in the United States, EJ initially addressed the intersections of race and environmental harm (Cutter 1995). In Iran, however, racial injustice has not been the primary axis of inequality; instead, environmental injustices have often reflected differences in class. The term "environmental justice" has only recently begun to appear in Iranian academic discourse, as environmental challenges are increasingly understood within a broader system of social and economic injustice that benefits some groups at the expense of others.

Iranian scholars have employed the concept of environmental justice to examine distributional and socio-spatial inequalities in cities and regions. Studies have explored the unequal distribution of green space in cities such as Zanjan, Tehran, and Isfahan (Milani et al. 2025; Anabestani et al. 2023; Ghalehtimouri et al. 2021; Najafi et al. 2024), housing inequalities in relation to climate justice (Suleimany 2023), and class-based disparities in exposure to environmental threats

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(Ghorbani et al. 2019; Najafi et al. 2024). Others have framed EJ within broader discussions of eco-coloniality and peripheral marginalization (Hassaniyan 2024; Wiktor-Mach et al. 2024; Jafari 2024). These studies investigate the historical, cultural, political, and economic mechanisms through which environmental harms and benefits are distributed unequally. Moreover, they critique the Iranian state's centralized management of large-scale resources, particularly water infrastructure and inter-basin water transfer (IBWT) projects, which systematically disadvantage ethnic minority regions to the benefit of the Persian-majority central plateau.

Building on this emerging perspective, this paper argues that current environmental challenges in Iran, such as increasing temperatures, urban air pollution, dust storms, droughts and water shortages, should be analyzed through a social justice framework. Environmental justice offers a valuable discursive tool for understanding these issues as part of a broader system of unequal distribution of wealth, power, and resources. Since gender has become a focal point in contemporary debates on injustice (especially during and after the 2022 Women, Life, Freedom movement), this moment presents an opportunity to activate the feminist potential within environmental justice and to strengthen the connection between women's struggles and environmental struggles.

In the current body of scholarship about Iran's environmental justice, gender has not yet become a central analytical category. One of the few exceptions is Marie Ranjbar's (2023) study of popular protests surrounding the Lake Orumiyeh crisis in Iranian Azerbaijan. Ranjbar uses gender to theorize resistance, state critique, and the community's deep emotional connection to the environment. Other studies have examined women's participation in environmental protection and activism in Iranian Kurdistan, emphasizing their roles in grassroots movements, organizational leadership, and resistance to patriarchal and state constraints (Wiktor-Mach et al. 2024). The disproportionate impacts of environmental policies on women have also been the focus of analysis. For instance, Jafari (2024) shows that the violence resulting from hydrological interventions in Khuzestan's water basin since the 1940s has affected women most severely, given their social roles and proximity to water resources.

These studies make important contributions by centering gender in their analyses. However, gender has yet to achieve phenomenological significance in most of this work. The present paper, therefore, has two aims: first, to strengthen the field of environmental justice studies by demonstrating that EJ is inherently a feminist project; and second, to articulate the contours of a feminist environmental justice framework in the context of Iran.

The Islamic Republic of Iran (IRI) has been in power since 1979 following a popular revolution. Although the revolution involved diverse groups with different agendas (and without reducing the current Iranian state simply to a theocracy) in the end, the clerical and theocratic factions claimed control and sought to eliminate their rivals. For women, this shift came at a high cost. Only two weeks after the revolution, laws that had previously supported women's rights in areas such as marriage, divorce, and inheritance were repealed. The new legal framework systematically disadvantaged women and privileged cisgender men. Short term after the revolution, women were asked to wear hijab in public.

The gendered policies of the IRI have been analyzed from multiple disciplinary perspectives

(Kian 2007; Hoodfar and Sadr 2010; Gould 2014). I argue that they must also be examined through the lens of critical environmental justice, as the IRI's discriminatory legal system has tangible environmental consequences for women's bodies and processes of social reproduction. In doing so, I draw on the emerging field of critical environmental justice, which, unlike traditional EJ research, pays closer attention to the body as an environmental scale and to the politics of social reproduction. This perspective offers the potential to correct one of the longstanding limitations of environmental justice scholarship: its insufficient attention to gender.

In this paper, through stories and accounts gathered from news agencies and social media, I will explore the experience of Iranian women of environmental injustice as raised from the discriminatory legal system that systematically harms women and other marginalized gendered bodies and disrupts their social reproduction. I argue that in a feminist approach to environmental justice, all forms of putting bodies in preventable danger and hazard, taking lives, injuring bodies, subsistence interruption, and imprisonment must be considered matters of environmental harm. Furthermore, not only environmental policies but also law-based gender inequalities and labor policies that directly or indirectly put individuals and communities in preventable danger must be investigated as topics of environmental justice scholarship.

Environmental Justice as a Feminist Field

Environmental justice is a movement in which women are most active. Women's participation and leadership in environmental justice movements is so high that Robert Verchick (1996) describes it as a feminist movement, and Bell and Braun (2010) call it gendered activism. Environmentalism provides a relatively safe and vital avenue for women's empowerment and for challenging patriarchal norms. In Iranian Kurdistan, for instance, it has become an important arena for advancing women's agency and collective action. Kurdish women increasingly participate in grassroots environmental movements, such as the Chiya Association (Anjoman-e Sabz-e Chiya), where engagement with environmental issues encourages broader political awareness and activism (Wiktor-Mach et al. 2024).

Despite the central role of women, many environmental justice scholars suggest that gender and sexuality remain relatively marginal in EJ studies, although in recent years there is a growing body of literature that identifies and addresses this paucity (MacGregor 2020; Bell 2016; Mallory 2013; Gaard 2017; MacGregor 2020; Buckingham and Kulcur 2010; Pellow 2017). These works show that environmental justice as a field of study has a deep capacity to be more critical and feminist.

Environmental justice is not only a women's movement but also inherently a feminist movement for three key reasons. First, the issues that environmental justice movements address are deeply rooted in a patriarchal society. Environmental justice movements emerged from feminist critiques of the patriarchal system, which influenced environmental law (Verchick 1996). These movements challenge distributional unfairness by exposing biases in environmental protection that overlook the experiences and values of those most affected, many of whom, in the context of the USA, were people of color. In contrast to classic perceptions of environment, the revolutionary notion of the environmental justice movement was that the environment is not only nature, but also the place of living, working, and playing (Taylor 2000).

Second, the strategies and goals of the environmental justice movement reflect feminist methods developed by women's rights activists and feminist scholars, particularly in the 1960s and 1970s (Taylor 2000). One feminist strategy employed by environmental justice movements is to expose patriarchy by understanding women's individual experiences, showing how what appears personal is, in fact, systemic and shared across the lives of many women. This approach shifts the focus from victim-blaming, which was and still is common, to highlighting social disparities as structural problems that require structural solutions. As Dorceta Taylor puts it:

“The unjust outcomes in life circumstances are attributed to pervasive and persistent societal racism rather than the victim's imperfections” (Taylor 2000, 548)

In the same vein, environmental justice movements framed environmental issues, such as unequal exposure to pollution, inadequate housing, or limited access to environmental amenities, as structural consequences of racism and systemic inequality, not as reflections of people's faults.

Moreover, the methods used by environmental justice movements are inspired by and borrowed from feminist movements. In academic research, methodologies such as feminist ethnography, community-based research, and participatory research have been employed by environmental justice scholars, although positivist methodology remains dominant (Bell 2016).

Third, the theories of environmental justice have the potential to be closely connected to feminist theories. Some scholars have suggested a connection between environmental justice concepts and feminist environmental disciplines, such as ecofeminism and feminist political ecology, and have adopted a multidisciplinary approach (Ducre 2018; Braun 2015). Specifically, the ecofeminist perspective appears to have a great capacity to analyze environmental injustice faced by women and gender minorities. Ecofeminists like Gaard (2017) show that issues like sexism, ageism, ableism, speciesism, and heterosexism all have environmental aspects, and thus environmental and climate justice movements must be able to include them and mobilize around them. Taking a more intersectional perspective that, in addition to race and income (the two areas of focus for traditional environmental justice studies), includes and analyzes the matter of gender is another theoretical way to make environmental justice a feminist field of study (Pellow 2017; Buckingham, and Kulcur 2010).

The lesson these feminist perspectives offer for environmental justice (both as a field of study and as a social movement) is the urgent need to be radically attentive to matters of scale, particularly by incorporating the scale of the body and taking social reproduction seriously. Such an approach calls for innovative methods that move beyond place-based analyses to account for environmental harms affecting specific groups, such as women and LGBTQ+ communities, who may inhabit the same physical spaces as others yet experience those environments very differently. This perspective challenges the methodological limitation of much environmental justice research that confines analysis to a fixed place or scale. The present study contributes to this critical reorientation.

Environmental Justice and the Question of Scale and Social Reproduction

One reason for the neglect of gender in environmental justice studies may lie in the issue of geography and scale. For a long time, environmental justice studies predominantly were

concerned with proximity analysis, meaning how a hazardous source is located close to a community of low-income and people of color. In other words, environmental justice studies traditionally look at the relationship between being a member of a marginalized population and being exposed to environmental harms or being deprived of environmental benefits. Women do not live in geographically concentrated spaces, as would racial/ethnic minorities or people in poverty. Therefore, the consequences of environmental injustice to women and the LGBTQ+ community occur at a scale that is often invisible to the first generation of environmental justice studies, which is the individual body and the household or family (Pellow 2016; Buckingham and Kulcur 2010).

Although place-bound environmental justice research has been widely criticized, it remains the dominant methodology, often limiting studies to a specific place and scale. To balance place-based analyses, we need to develop innovative approaches that go beyond particular locations. Therefore, A feminist environmental justice approach must be multi-scalar. The body, home, community, and surrounding ecosystems are all gendered environments in feminist texts (Sze 2006; Buckingham and Kulcur 2010).

The bodily scale enhances our understanding of gender, race, nature, and culture. David Pellow (2017) argues that scale is deeply racialized, gendered, and classed, and it can be either spatial or temporal. The scale of the body can also transform our understanding of the environment, nature, and land. Ecofeminist scholars, in particular, have examined the body as a discursive site through which the hierarchical dualism of man/logic over woman/nature is produced and sustained. Ecofeminism exposes the intersections between gender inequality and ecological degradation, revealing how systems of domination over women and over nature are mutually reinforcing (Demirci 2025). The body, as the “first environment”, must therefore be explicitly recognized as a site of environmental injustice (Sze 2006; Buckingham and Kulcur 2010). Prominent ecofeminist, Rachel Stain (2004), suggests that

“When we view our bodies as ‘home’ as ‘lands’ and ‘homes’ and ‘environments,’ that have been placed at risk, stolen from us, and even killed due to social and physical harms that maybe exacerbated due to our gender and sexuality, we may understand the need for new perspectives on environmental justice that encompass such factors within our analysis”.

Considering the *body* as the environment helps us understand that when marginalized groups of humans are rendered and treated as not fully human, this would be a matter of environmental justice because it threatens one's health and life chances. A feminist scalar approach is a better recognition of the porosity of boundaries between the public and private realms and the micro-scales and environmental harms that could occur within them. This approach is deeply intersectional. It views the body as a site of struggles, particularly the bodies of people of color, indigenous peoples, LGBTQ+ folks, women, immigrants, and working-class people, along with bodies of land, water, and other animals. Pellow (2017) refers to a powerful quote from Chicana lesbian feminist scholar Cherríe Moraga, who writes:

“Land remains the common ground for all radical action. But land is more than rocks and trees. ... For immigrants and natives alike, land is also the factories where we work, the water our children drink, and the housing project where we live. For women, lesbians, and gay men, land is that physical mass called our bodies”

On the other hand, focusing solely on the body must not lead environmental justice research to another single-scale analysis. Instead, we need to consider how environmental injustice occurs at multiple scales, from the bodily level to the global scale. For example, water scarcity in parts of the world, such as the Middle East, creates competition among nation-states over water resources, leading to extensive dam construction projects. These projects cause issues like dust storms in downstream regions where rivers and wetlands have dried up due to upstream dams. When a woman in southern Iraq suffers from frequent dust pollution on a bodily scale, her suffering is linked to a decision made in Turkey (Bastan et al. 2013). A multi-scalar approach enables us to connect hazards in one place with harm in another. In the era of globalization, we cannot escape the environmental consequences of harmful decisions.

Feminist political ecology scholars have shown that gendered access to land and natural resources operates across all scales, not only within households or local contexts (Nightingale 2006). There is a systemic connection between the exploitation of nature and the exploitation of life (Fernandes et al. 2023). Women's unpaid and often invisible labor in social reproduction is closely tied to access to and control over land, particularly under conditions of capitalist expansion and dispossession (Fernandez 2018). In India, for example, when working-class households face income deficits due to land dispossession and drought, their survival increasingly depends on non-capitalist forms of production, often referred to as "domestic economies." Women's intensified labor in activities such as preparing cow dung cakes, food processing, and collecting water or firewood, became essential for maintaining household consumption at a minimum level (Naidu and Ossome 2016).

This example shows how micro-scale and macro-scale land regimes are interconnected. Additionally, it suggests an epistemological approach to considering scale in environmental justice scholarship by examining the arena of *social reproduction*. Social reproduction encompasses a range of activities, behaviors, responsibilities, and relationships that ensure the daily and generational social, emotional, moral, and physical reproduction of people (Meehan and Stauss 2015). It is a profoundly spatial phenomenon that emerges as a distinct set of social activities with the inception of capitalism. Therefore, "It is not so much what women do that makes their work invisible, but where women do it" (Winders and Smith 2019, 872).

The geography of social reproduction is often centered around the home. Social relations within the home, which serve as a site for reproduction, recreation, and increasingly, paid work, are often neglected in environmental justice analyses (Buckingham and Kulcur 2010). Unpaid and low-paid domestic work, primarily performed by women, creates a distinct relationship with the environment. A domestic worker, much more than a wage-earner, depends on access to non-commodified and public goods (meaning nature) for subsistence (Naidu and Ossome 2016). Moreover, homes remain unsupervised and potentially hazardous spaces, unlike other workplaces (Buckingham and Kulcur 2010).

Examining the home at the bodily scale reveals additional dimensions of environmental injustice experienced by women. The home is often a site of domestic abuse, which studies show increases during times of disaster or environmental degradation (Sety et al. 2014). Evidence from around the world indicates that domestic violence rose sharply during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdowns (Fawole et al. 2021; Lyons and Brewer 2021; Piquero et al. 2021; Zhang 2020). Domestic abuse includes a wide range of actions, from physical violence to financial abuse. The

latter is one of the most overlooked forms through which the home becomes a site of entrapment for women. Financial abuse can lead to deprivation of food, healthcare, and other basic needs, directly harming women's bodies. These constraints are deeply rooted in patriarchal systems and are often reinforced by legal frameworks. For instance, laws that designate the husband as the head of the household and undervalue women's economic contributions further limit women's control over financial matters. Such dynamics deserve greater attention within environmental justice scholarship.

In the next section, I turn to the context of Iran and, drawing on cases reported in news outlets and across social media, examine how the gendered legal system has intensified the burdens of Iran's environmental crises on women's bodies and within geographies such as the home and the workplace. Through these stories, the paper suggests approaches for examining environmental issues more critically and comprehensively.

A Feminist Environmental Justice for Iranian Women

How can the gender policies of the Iranian government inform us about environmental injustice? The answer to this question helps us to understand why struggles for gender equality are interconnected with environmental struggles. It will also help consolidate intersectional, multidimensional, and multi-scalar efforts toward social change. This paper examines the multiple scales at which environmental injustice emerges in the Iranian context, considers different categories of social difference, and critically interrogates prevailing definitions of "environment" and "environmental harm."

One of this paper's key contributions is the exploration of areas not traditionally regarded as environmental and of laws not typically classified as environmental legislation. When the body is understood as an environment, the definition of environmental harm must be expanded to include bodily harm as well (Pellow 2016). This perspective responds to the geography-centric and place-based approaches that dominate traditional environmental justice scholarship, a limitation that contributes to the neglect of gender analysis in this field. Furthermore, this paper challenges the conventional assumption that environmental injustice primarily results from environmental decisions made by authorities. It argues instead that other components of the legal system can also produce environmental injustice, even when they are not explicitly environmental in nature.

Scholars argue that the environmental injustices experienced by women are rooted in interwoven and enduring capitalist and patriarchal structures (Bell 2016). Iran is not an exception in this regard. In the Iranian context, multiple forms of environmental harm are imposed on women's bodies and lives, arising from the legal system, punitive institutions, and labor policies. The most visible post-revolutionary gender-based policy in Iran is the *forced hijab*, which is a set of strict dress codes that women wear in public. Among other limitations, compulsory dress codes are threatening to Iranian working-class women and increase the risk of occupational hazards. Compulsory hijab is often prioritized over the safety and comfort of female workers.

One of the most horrible incidents that attracted public attention was a 21-year-old worker who lost her life in a horrendous incident. Marzieh Taherian was a textile worker in Semnan, an industrial city 137 miles east of Tehran. On November 6, 2021, Maqna'e (a modified headscarf designed to cover the head, neck, and chest area) was stuck in the spinning machine and pulled

in her head. She died dreadfully (“Female Worker Dead After Veil Caught in Machinery at Factory” 2021). Forced hijab-related incidents are not rare in the workplace. Similar incidents were reported in 2018 and 2022 (*Iran Kargar* 2022).

The compulsory hijab and the austere methods used to impose and monitor it undermine workplace safety protocols and place women in preventable and unnecessary danger. These avoidable harms directly target women’s bodies, increasing illness and vulnerability to occupational hazards. This pattern is not unique to Iran. Numerous studies have shown that, globally, women experience higher morbidity rates than men (Khamu and Langstieh 2015; Popli 2005; Bhatia et al. 2007; Bhosale and Devi 2008; Rahman 2009). In Iran, this global and historically rooted trend is further intensified through the imposition of discriminatory laws. These incidents cannot be reduced to shortcomings in labor regulations alone, as the harms are fully preventable by applying the same safety standards to all workers, regardless of gender. Women’s experience in this context is shaped by the intersection of gender and class.

Even if not life-threatening, forced hijab can make female workers' lives more tedious than their male counterparts. When exposed to the same weather and temperature conditions, female workers in all industries experience more heat stress than their male counterparts. In 2012, a woman posted an article on the National Oil Company website, complaining about the dress code that female personnel had to wear in the harsh, hot weather of southern Iran. For women, the dress code included black trousers, a long black manteau (a long, loose, thick fabric, and long-sleeved dress that women are required to wear in public), and a black maqna'e. This woman's demand is for the color of their uniform to be changed from black to white, in order to absorb less heat (Maljoo 2012). She wrote, "As you know, sometimes the temperature is as high as 50 °C in this region. When combined with humidity, it is unbearable for women to wear dark clothes that absorb heat. We respectfully ask for a revision of the women's dress code so we can wear white clothes." However, this demand was rejected.

Her male colleagues' responses to her post reveal another layer of environmental harm caused by discriminatory laws against women: This legal system disturbs women's social reproduction by limiting their access to the job market. In response to that woman worker, many comments pointed out that if she could not bear the dress code, she had better go back to her kitchen and leave the position for a young man who truly needed it. Globally and historically, the energy industry has been dominated by men. For instance, in the USA, approximately 82 percent of jobs in the oil and gas industries are held by men (McKee, 2014), and in Iran, this number is roughly 92 percent (Petro-Energy Information Network, 2017). As an example, one of the largest petrochemical companies in Khuzestan and Iran had only 12 women employed in 2020, compared to 473 men (Khuzestan Petrochemical Company, 2020).

Over the past decade, international sanctions have intensified economic hardship, pushing a growing number of women into the informal labor market in order to supplement household income. In this context, street vending has become a common occupation for individuals excluded from formal employment. However, the marginalization of women from industrial workplaces and their consequent relegation to unpaid domestic labor or precarious informal work predates recent economic pressures. In the first decade following the 1979 Revolution, women’s labor force participation dropped sharply from 13.8 to 8.9 percent, a decline driven largely by the exclusion of working-class women. Many women who did not comply with the post-Revolution

legal and social regulations left their jobs voluntarily, while many others were dismissed (Nomani and Behdad 2006).

In such condition, the compulsory dress code makes long hours of outdoor work particularly arduous for female street vendors, especially given the high temperatures in many Iranian cities during the spring and summer months. Iran is experiencing some of the most severe impacts of global climate change. Over the past fifty years, Tehran has warmed by 2°C, nearly double the global average, and the frequency of extremely hot days and nights has increased substantially. Recent decades have witnessed unprecedented heat waves, with specific months and years recording the highest temperatures on record (Iran Open Data Center 2024). To avoid harassment by police and municipal agents, who routinely target street vendors, many women vendors adopt even stricter forms of bodily covering than other women, thereby intensifying their exposure to extreme heat.

In addition to heat-related risks, women street vendors are exposed to persistent bodily harms, including sexual harassment (Saba 2021) and police violence (Tadrissi 2022; Fararu 2022; Asre Iran 2016). These examples highlight the limitations of environmental approaches that focus solely on regulatory measures. Such approaches provide minimal protection for working-class women, as the sources of environmental injustice in their lives are deeply rooted in the direct harms imposed on their bodies and everyday experiences.

As noted above, greater attention to the sphere of social reproduction and its geographies is necessary to take gender seriously within EJ studies. The intersection of class and gender in political power has resulted in more working-class women being bound to unwaged, unsupervised, and potentially hazardous spaces, including the home. Homes are sites of domestic abuse that include a wide range of actions, from physical violence to food and medical deprivation and coercive control. For many women worldwide, the home can easily turn into a temporary or permanent prison. A locked door is a form of domestic abuse. As Rob Nixon (2011) notes, "Doors for women are often long-term, nonlethal weapons that leave no telltale bloody trail; doors don't bear witness to a single, decisive blow." If the body is a site of environmental injustice, then all forms of captivity are environmental injustices since they harm the body (Pellow 2017).

Homes, particularly kitchens, function as small-scale geographies of pollutants. Cooking, cleaning, heating, and the use of pesticides all contribute to indoor pollution (Vardoulakis et al., 2020; Baumgartner et al., 2011; Kadir et al., 2010), which disproportionately affects women due to their traditional domestic responsibilities. In Iran, the impact of indoor pollution on women is most evident in the increased cardiovascular risks associated with the use of combustion fuels and exposure to heavy metals through contaminated house dust (Samet et al., 2016; Moradnia et al., 2023). The head of Shahid Beheshti University of Medical Sciences reported that 85 percent of housewives are at risk of developing lung disease due to poor-quality cooking appliances and pollution generated during food preparation (Ahsanipour 2019). Continuous exposure to bleaching agents and other chemical disinfectants is also linked to a higher risk of serious pulmonary diseases (Salehi 2019). Moreover, housewives face an elevated risk of depression compared with women who work outside the home. This is often due to the perception that their extensive labor is undervalued or unrecognized as legitimate work, which negatively affects self-esteem and independence and may contribute to anger and depression (Vardoulakis et al. 2020).

Again, if home is a site of environmental justice, the laws and policies that confine women to home must be targeted by environmental justice activists, including policies that push women to home and limit their ability to earn money. Preventing or limiting someone's decent livelihood is a form of slow violence, a violence that occurs gradually and out of sight, a violence of delayed destruction dispersed across time and space (Nixon 2011). This has direct and indirect threatening consequences for women's bodily autonomy. Limited access to funds, credit, and health insurance restricts women's control over their bodies in making decisions regarding their wellbeing. Moreover, several studies show that a greater economic independence improves a woman's bargaining position and increases her "fallback positions" (her ability to leave the relationship), thus reducing the threat of domestic violence (Eggers Del Campo and Steinert 2022; Dildar 2021; Molina et al. 2025; Raj et al. 2018).

One of the few studies examining the outcomes of the 1960s land reform in Iran highlights the profound impact of land dispossession on women. In western Iran, the land reform led to a dramatic increase in women's suicides, largely linked to exposure to domestic violence (Karami and Rahmanian 2017; Anbari and Bahrami 2010). Under the land reform law, women's reproductive labor, although essential to agricultural production, was not classified as *work*, and households were defined in ways that excluded women who owned land independently of their husbands. The authors note that the western provinces, which had the highest number of small female landowners and experienced extensive dispossession, also recorded the highest rates of self-immolation in subsequent decades. This case illustrates the consequences of failing to recognize women's social reproductive work and underscores the importance of considering social reproduction as a domain in which environmental injustice can occur. This outcome was not inevitable; other countries' experiences show alternative possibilities. For example, in Zimbabwe, radical land redistribution significantly increased women's individual land ownership, from 5 percent prior to reform to 10–28 percent afterward, often benefiting vulnerable groups such as widows (Ossome 2021).

Even when women participate in economic activities, they are constantly threatened by forces that can arbitrarily disrupt their social reproductive activities. In Hengam, a southern island of Iran, fishing has traditionally been a job for both men and women. Several years of drought, in addition to leasing out the right of fishing to transnational companies who clean out fish resources in the Persian Gulf much faster than the local fishers can keep up with, has put the local communities, whose livelihood is dependent on fishing, in a precarious situation (Radio Farda 2020). Meanwhile, an additional layer of hardship exists for women. The authorities most often refuse to grant permission for women to fish. Officials have explicitly stated that fishing is not "a woman's job" when fisherwomen seek licenses. These women often fish alone, without licenses. As a result, fisherwomen do not receive the same support as male fishers, including health insurance, subsidized fuel, and access to banking loans, leaving them with unstable and minimal incomes, a significant portion of which must go to the cost of fuel and repairs. Even if licenses are eventually issued, authorities have proposed issuing one permit for every two fisherwomen. The fisherwomen question why they, whose work is no different from men's, must share a joint license (Zargari 2021). This situation puts a heavier burden of climate change on women. In this case, even when fish remain available, women are systematically deprived of the opportunity to earn a decent livelihood from them.

In Iran, a growing body of literature within the tradition of feminist political ecology shows that

gender inequalities in patriarchal communities are among the primary factors contributing to women's vulnerability to climate change (Moayedi et al., 2022; Tafti and Pourmohsen, 2023). To understand this dynamic in Iran, it is necessary to situate these vulnerabilities within the country's legal system, which can exacerbate women's exposure to natural disasters. In 2019, a series of devastating floods struck southern Iran. A piece of news was exemplary of how legal systems can exacerbate the impacts of natural disasters on women: two days after a flood destroyed her home and belongings, a woman sought to take her sick infant (ill due to the lack of clean water after the flood) to the hospital while the father was away. However, she confronts an exceptional barrier: the hospital does not accept the child without the father's presence or permission (Amidi 2019). As the ambulance nurse explained, "Either her husband has to come with the infant, or he must sign a form stating that he refused to go to the hospital on his own responsibility. We can't do anything else, because it would cause trouble."

By law, Iranian women do not have legal authority over their children. This fact adds another layer to women's vulnerability to natural disasters, directly arising from the low status of women in the legal system. In this legal system, women's roles are defined as caregivers and are responsible for the wellbeing of children. Yet, this role does not carry the necessary legal authority to act effectively in emergencies, subjecting women to double pressure and making them more vulnerable to natural disasters and environmental issues.

A form of state-sanctioned violence disproportionately targets women's bodies: the hijab police². Established in 2007, this police force is tasked with detaining women whose hijab is deemed *improperly worn*, a criterion that is vaguely defined. Since its inception, thousands of women in major cities have been detained daily for perceived violations of dress code regulations. Violence and the use of extreme force by the hijab police are not rare when a targeted woman resists. On social media, one can find several video clips showing such violence. One video recording that went viral in the summer of 2022 shows a woman who is trying to stop a hijab police patrol vehicle that her daughter is apparently in. She shouts, "My daughter is sick; let her go." In this case, the dress code policy again cancels all health-related precautions and puts lives in preventable danger.

For pregnant women, women with severe health conditions, and those with anxiety disorders, the hijab police can be a health threat. Posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) is prevalent among those who have experienced hijab police encounters. Based on the information revealed by a psychiatrist at Roozbeh Hospital in Tehran, for these women, PTSD expresses itself in various ways: they frequently experience memory flashbacks, tachycardia, and shortness of breath. Some of them said that they could not walk on the street where they were arrested. In one case, a woman locked herself at home for two months (agoraphobia) after her arrest (Iran International 2022). Discriminatory gender policies injure women's deepest emotions and can prevent them from leading healthy and happy lives.

One influential incident that fueled a massive protest around Iran was the death of Mahsa Jina Amini at the hijab police station while she was in custody. This incident was a turning point in the resistance movement against gender discrimination in Iran and brought the Kurdish slogan of "Women, Life, Freedom" into the political sphere of Iran. Jina was a 22-year-old Iranian Kurdish

² Gasht-e Ershad in Farsi. sometimes referred to as the Morality Police

woman who visited her relatives in Tehran when taken to a police station by the hijab police. There are a few accounts of how she died, from being beaten in the head to having a stroke following an anxiety attack at the station. Both accounts show the treatment of the dress code policy, which leaves scars on women's bodies and even causes their deaths. At the same time, the mass protest that came after this incident shows that the woman's body, as much as the site of environmental injustice, is the site of resistance and struggle.

The cases I provided in this paper show that environmental injustice can be seen in the scales and areas that are not conventionally seen as the environment, yet the consequences of these types of injustice can be environmental. All these examples need to be more carefully scrutinized, but it is important that environmental justice scholars, as Gaard puts it, "start asking different questions" (Gaard 2017).

Conclusion and Lessons of the Women's Struggle for Environmental Justice Struggle

As discussed earlier, environmental justice is inherently intertwined with feminist politics, even though gender has not been a central analytic focus in most EJ scholarship. EJ movements have long drawn on feminist strategies -organizationally, intellectually, and methodologically. One contribution of this paper is to demonstrate how academic work in environmental justice must take feminist insights seriously, including the insistence on the body and the home as key analytical scales, the centrality of social reproduction, and the structuring force of gendered legal regimes. On the ground, too, environmental movements have much to learn from feminist struggles. In Iran, mobilization around environmental issues is considerably younger than feminist organizing, and there remains a great deal that can be borrowed from the latter's repertoire.

Today, through persistent everyday resistance and, at moments, through mass mobilization and violent state confrontation -as in the 2022 *Women Life Freedom* uprising- Iranian women have managed to challenge and weaken some of the most oppressive aspects of the legal system. Forced hijab, for instance, has become significantly harder for authorities to enforce. These shifts were won through a transformation in popular discourse. For decades, women's rights were framed as marginal to "more pressing" national concerns, such as economic hardship. Today, however, women's rights have become one of the most contested and widely debated issues in Iran's public sphere. Environmental movements can draw from this transformation. They must contest the prevailing discourse that casts environmental problems as secondary to economic crises, unemployment, or poverty. Like feminists, environmental activists must demonstrate the urgency of ecological degradation and reveal the intimate connections between environmental crises and the very socioeconomic problems they are often asked to defer to. They must also demand and articulate alternatives that do not rely on the continual extraction of what is assumed to be the "free gift of nature."

Another key lesson from feminist movements is the importance of bringing political struggle down to the scale of everyday life. Feminist activists have consistently shown how compulsory hijab affects women not only as a matter of rights and freedoms but also through its daily intrusions into mobility, safety, health, and dignity. Similarly, environmental activism must continue its shift away from a narrow conservationist frame toward the lived conditions of social reproduction. This shift must go further by incorporating the bodily scale into everyday

environmental discourse, particularly through the experiences of marginalized groups such as women, LGBTQ+ people, immigrants, and ethnic minorities. Moreover, as this paper has argued, the small-scale geographies like home, prison, workplaces, and care infrastructures must be central in the environmental justice movement.

Feminist movements also offer lessons in persistence and strategic innovation. Iranian women have sustained their claims through creative tactics that extend far beyond formal legal channels: asserting bodily sovereignty in public, using social media to circulate evidence and build solidarity, staging performative actions, and turning the city itself into a space of feminist claim-making. Each of these strategies provides helpful guidance for environmental movements seeking to expand their political imagination and reach.

Finally, these forms of practice must be accompanied and strengthened by rigorous academic work. Intellectual labor is not secondary; it provides the conceptual, historical, and analytical foundations that allow movements to articulate their demands, frame their grievances, and imagine alternatives. Recognizing the many points of overlap between feminist and environmental movements allows these lessons to travel organically from one sphere of struggle to the other.

Environmental justice studies are expanding rapidly, with more scholars critically examining the field and proposing methodological and theoretical improvements. This paper, by assessing some of the challenges faced by Iranian women, has outlined methodological directions through which environmental justice research can engage more deeply with feminist insights and strengthen the field in both theory and practice. In addition to the areas discussed above, future research in Iran using a similar approach should pay closer attention to environmental injustices arising at the intersection of gender, citizenship (for example, Afghan immigrants and refugees), and sexuality (LGBTQ+ communities). As Mollett and Faria (2012, 116) note, “gender does not act alone.” Moreover, beyond the home and the workplace (addressed in this paper), prisons, detention centers, care infrastructures, refugee camps, displacement sites, and border zones are all critical sites that warrant investigation in order to radically conceptualize environmental injustice in Iran radically.

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